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TOWARDS A MANIFESTO FOR PLACE QUALITY BASED ON THE EXPERIENCE ECONOMY

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Abstract: With the works of Pine and Gilmore, the experience economy is best recognized in the fields of strategic marketing and consumer behavior. We hope to demonstrate that the fundamental exclusivities of experience economy had been proposed and discussed in urban studies a decade before its introduction by Pine and Gilmore by examining the article "Toward an urban design manifesto" written by Allan Jacobs and Donald Appleyard (1987), and that there are significant similarities between them. This raises the possibility that their essay may be seen as a ground-breaking piece, connecting urban studies and quality of place with the experience economy. Despite the fact that there are few researches on experience economy in urban settings today, Jacobs and Appleyard proposed it as a key aim for achieving a better urban living and a healthier environment.

Keywords: Standardized offerings; Physical landscape of cities; The economic value of goods; Metaphor.

Introduction

In the current world full of mass production and standardized offerings, people as consumers, are leaning toward the more experiential ones. As Pine and Gilmore (2013) believe, “we have now entered an experience economy” where symbolic concepts and meanings determine the economic value of goods (Jameson, 1991; Pine & Gilmore, 1998) and “people buy things not only for what they can do, but also for what they mean” . Therefore, postmodern society tends toward the experience industries which transforms it into an experience society (Schulze, 1992). To compete and achieve the maximum possible value of such a market, Pine and Gilmore declare that companies must increase the value of products and services by enhancing their aesthetic and experimental dimensions. Cities and urban environments are not an exception to this trend because many experiences are place-bound, thus they are able to change the physical landscape of cities to experiencescapes. In this regard, it is claimed that the new experience economy is able to enhance the quality of place and change the identity of the city to an experience city. 2. The experience economy: evidence in leading debates. The notion of the experience economy, introduced by Pine and Gilmore in 1998 for the first time, has brought new theoretical and empirical insights and many studies in different fields have been conducted using the experience model (4Es) and principles presented by them. However, this approach was rarely addressed in leading debates within urban studies (Jeannerat, 2015). Considering these, coming upon an article on urban planning and design with the title of “Toward an urban design manifesto” by Jacobs and Appleyard (1987) caught our attention for its several commonalities with Pine and Gilmore's explanation of experience economy and prompted us to examine the roots of experience economy in this significant article after several decades of its publication. In the aforementioned article, the authors present a new urban design manifesto and to do this, they make a review of two modern movements and the problems they brought for modern urban design, and after that, they propose a number of essential goals for the

future of a good urban environment and life. What made this article stand out to us, is that first, the descriptions of two goals i.e. a. access to opportunity, imagination, and joy, and b. authenticity and meaning remind us of the experience economy concept introduced by Pine & Gilmore, 1998 a decade after the publication of this article, and second, it links the quality of place (environment) with the experiences that the city offers.

MAIN BODY

Before getting into the two mentioned goals in Jacobs and Appleyard's article, it is necessary to take a brief look at the experience economy exclusivities proposed by Pine and Gilmore. There is a very famous metaphor by them, stating “work is theater and every business a stage” which explains that “anyone working in front of customers must act in a way that draws them into the experience”. What Pine and Gilmore want to achieve by using the terms of theater, stage, and acting in this metaphor, is the engagement of customers and creation of memorable experiences for them, which is very crucial for an experience product and value creation. Under this notion, there are four experience realms, that help the design of experiences. Authenticity is another issue that they point out. In their opinion authenticity is “the new consumer sensibility” and therefore people see the world in the context of fake and real. With this in mind, we continue our discussion by bringing some parts of the mentioned goals in Jacobs and Appleyard's work below so that we can examine them more thoroughly.

Characteristics	Pine & Gilmore	Jacobs & Appleyard	Schematic depiction
Entertainment	✓	✓	
Educational	✓	✓	
Escapist	✓	✓	
Esthetic	✓	not explicitly mentioned	
Authenticity	✓	✓	
Story telling	✓	✓	
Theatre	Work	City	
Actors	Workers	Citizens	
Participation	mostly passive	Active	
Experience generation	first (staging)	second/ third (co-creation/ self-direction)	
Company/ planner	main role	Preparer	
Role of experiences	getting maximum possible value	achieving good urban life and quality environment	

“People should find the city a place where they can break from traditional molds, extend their experience, meet new people, learn other viewpoints, have fun. They should find the city an enlightening cultural experience. A city should have magical places where fantasy is possible, a counter to and an escape from the mundaneness of everyday work and living. ... People need an escape from the seriousness and meaning of the everyday. The city ... is theater, a stage upon which citizens can display themselves and see others. It has magic, or should have, and that depends on a certain sensuous, hedonistic mood, on signs, on night lights, on fantasy, color, and other imagery. There can be parts of the city where belief can

be suspended, just as in the experience of fiction. It may be that such places have to be framed so that people know how to act. Until now such fantasy and experiment have been attempted mostly by commercial facilities, at rather low levels of quality and aspiration, seldom deeply experimental. One should not have to travel as far as the Himalayas or the South Sea Islands to stretch one's experience. ... There should be a place for community utopias; for historic, natural, and anthropological evocations of the modern city” “... An authentic city is one where the origins of things and places are clear. All this means an urban environment should reveal its significant meanings ... The city should symbolize the moral issues of society and educate its citizens to an awareness of them. That does not mean everything has to be laid out as on a supermarket shelf. A city should present itself as a readable story, in an engaging and, if necessary, provocative way, for people are indifferent to the obvious, overwhelmed by complexity. A city's offerings should be revealed or they will be missed.”

In the article, the authors represent a view about city, stating “city is theater” which is comparable with Pine and Gilmore's metaphor of “work is theater”. In a city, citizens are those acting on the stage which the city has prepared for them, just like workers acting in front of customers. But here, there is a difference between these two phrases which can be referred to experience economy generations. While in Pine and Gilmore's metaphor, stages and actors are used as resources to arouse the feelings of the customers who mostly participate as passive audiences here, from the authors' point of view, citizens are active and so they can be called co-creators or even self-directors of the experiences; therefore, the role of city planners is to prepare the stage for citizens' participation to create their own experiences. Upon this city stage, citizens can display themselves, see others, expand their experience, and get cultural experiences (Jacobs & Appleyard, 1987). Such ideas about the city can be seen in urban studies recently done with inspiration from the experience economy approach. For example, Lorentzen (2015) regards experience economy as a planning approach and by using Pine and Gilmore's metaphor argues that “planning is theatre and every city is a stage”. This means that planning is about changing the city via staging it in order to create urban quality places

through engaging citizens in experiences. Pine and Gilmore (2013) explain that by understanding work is theater and using it in practice, even the most mundane tasks will turn into memorable offerings to engage and satisfy customers. It seems that Jacobs and Appleyard also had the same approach dealing with the mundaneness of city life. They declare that planners take cities too seriously while people need to escape from this seriousness, mundaneness, and meaning of everyday life by magical places and exploitation of fantasy, hedonistic moods, or in terms of experience economy, memorable experiences. Furthermore, it is said that the city should educate its citizens and they should learn other viewpoints. Here, similar to the explanation of experience realms, education is not necessarily formal but rather has a much wider socio-cultural context, rooted in human life. These aspects are common with Pine and Gilmore's view when they emphasize seeing all 'four Es' to avoid focusing on just the realm of 'entertainment'; because staging experiences is not just about entertaining and fun but also including customer engagement. Applying all of the experience realms together brings about the creation of an urban stage which supports citizens' active participation and engagement (Pine & Gilmore, 1998). 'Authenticity and meaning' is another goal, Jacobs and Appleyard consider essential for a good urban environment. They illustrate an authentic city where all origins are obvious and urban environment reveals its significant meanings. This is what Pine and Gilmore believe experiences should offer in order to respond to the new consumer sensibility, because in the world of experiences, people choose offerings based on how real they perceive them and look for originality and real values. This is the same for urban destinations, contemporary visitor expects authentic city experiences also describe authentic places as places, having meaning for their users and as a result more efficiently attract residents, tourists, and investors. The most attractive cities are the ones with authentic characteristics which have a very close relationship with stories and are strengthened by them. In fact, one of the ways for creating an authentic experience is to use a story. It seems that Jacobs and Appleyard were aware of this relationship and to promote the authenticity of the city, they emphasize that the city should show itself as a readable story. Having such a story about

the city in the context of urban staging, gives more meaningful experiences to citizens who are involved and aware of their city.

Conclusion

Linking the quality of place with experiences a city offers and the existence of several similarities between Jacobs and Appleyard's perspective and the experience economy approach, indicates that they were one step ahead in understanding the role and importance of experiences in urban life. What they expected from a city was the experience one and believed that experiences are an inseparable part of a good city and a quality environment that has recently got more attention and been up for the new discussions in urban studies and planning. Besides all commonalities discussed above, Jacobs and Appleyard's attention to the experiential aspect of the city reminds us that experiences are much more important than being just a new approach, and planners do not have to consider and apply it in city planning merely because of new market demands, but in fact they should pay attention to experiences due to the role they play in improving the quality of place and following that, quality of urban life. Although most of the new urban studies about experiences have been done because of the needs of postmodern society - after the introduction of experience economy notion by Pine and Gilmore - and also to get the maximum possible value, the authors put the quality of urban life and citizens' happiness first. Examining the roots of experience in the article "Toward an urban design manifesto" shows the importance of paying attention to the experiences as a bigger goal for achieving better cities. It also indicates that urban planning literature has theoretical support independent from the experience economy approach but very similar to its founders, Pine and Gilmore's ideas.

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